

An analysis of lexical and syntactic errors in the Urdu translation of the Punjab Textbook Board's English literature

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English, a second language in Pakistan, is challenging for many intermediate learners who rely on guidebooks for Urdu translations of English literature. This study examines lexical and syntactic errors in these translations, focusing on the Dogar Publisher's guidebook for Intermediate Part 1. Using Baker's (1992) translation strategies, the analysis revealed significant errors at both lexical and syntactic levels. Lexically, discrepancies were observed, with some English words remaining untranslated or being inaccurately translated. Syntactically, errors were identified in sentence construction, leading to a lack of conveying the intended meaning. Additionally, certain parts of the sentences were left untranslated. To improve translated materials, publishers should prioritize precise translation, address lexical and syntactic challenges, and employ qualified translators to prevent errors that may impede exam success and hinder English proficiency. Addressing these issues is essential for improving exam performance and language skills for guidebook users.

Keywords: English Learning; Goofs; Lexical Errors; Syntax Errors; Semantic Errors; Translation

1. Introduction

The introduction of English to the region now known as Pakistan occurred during British colonization (Mahboob, 2002). Today, the acquisition of English is a global necessity. Cook (2008) described English as a "hypercentral language," permeating all cultures and societies worldwide. Whether by necessity or choice, the English language has spread across the globe (Sharifian, 2009). It holds a dominant position as a foreign language and is widely used in educational institutions as the medium of instruction (Chang, 2010; cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2003, 2007a, 2008, 2020, 2021, 2023b). Following the independence of Pakistan, English was initially taught in elite, English-medium schools (Batoool et al., 2022).

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Farman (2019) explored syntactic errors in the English-Urdu translation of Lahore, highlighting the influence of Urdu and the limited understanding of English among intermediate students in government colleges. Shiddiq et al. (2023) identified 402 lexical and grammatical errors in Indonesian-English translations by EFL learners, focusing on phonological, lexico-semantic, and cultural factors. Jabak (2023) examined lexical, syntactic, and transliteration errors in Omani students translating English news headlines into Arabic. Similarly, Obeidat (2022) analyzed syntactic errors in the translation of COVID-19 documents from English to Arabic, while Putri and Sujarwati (2021) studied syntactic errors in student abstracts, primarily related to tense, advocating for enhanced teaching of English tenses to non-native speakers. These examples show that analyzing translation errors is critical for identifying common problems and their causes, helping students improve both their translation skills and English proficiency. This study investigates translation errors from English to Urdu, identifying the most prevalent issues and offering insights into their causes.

In Pakistan, the 'grammar-translation method' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2006) remains a dominant approach to English instruction, with students relying on translation to comprehend English. Although much research has addressed the challenges students face, there is limited focus on translation 'errors' in English literature guidebooks. Translation is a skill requiring the accurate interpretation of a source text into another language while preserving meaning, style, and intent. Proficiency in both the foreign language and the native tongue, along with cultural knowledge, is essential.

Despite substantial research on translation errors at the syntactic and lexical levels, few studies address the translation of English literature in guidebooks. This study aims to (a) analyze translation errors from English into Urdu, (b) identify the most common types, and (c) offer insights into their causes. Ultimately, it seeks to assist students in improving their translation skills and English proficiency. The research questions guiding this study are:

1. What are the lexical translation errors in Intermediate textbooks translated into Urdu from English fiction texts?
2. What are the syntactic translation errors in Intermediate guidebooks translated into Urdu from English fiction texts?

This study focuses on translation errors found in the Urdu version of Intermediate English fiction texts, specifically examining selected chapters from a Dogar Publishers guidebook for Intermediate Part 1. It addresses a previously underexplored area: translation from English to Urdu in Pakistan, particularly within the context of multilingualism. This research is significant for both academic and societal contexts in Pakistan, contributing to evolving research paradigms in the field of translation.

2. Background

The emergence of English as a global language (cf. Daftarifard & Salmani Nodoushan, 2011; Salmani Nodoushan, 2023a) has been extensively studied, with scholars examining its historical development, sociolinguistic implications, and influence on societies worldwide (e.g., Balosa, 2024; Chaka, 2024; Hannaford & Alexander, 2024; Huang, 2024; Koné, 2024; Mapuya, 2024; Mostafa & Jahan, 2024; Ndlangamandla, 2024; Nkhi & Shange, 2024; Sari et al., 2024; Xu & Fang, 2024). Crystal (2003) traced the historical evolution of English from a regional dialect to a global 'lingua franca' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2024), emphasizing the role of key historical events, such as colonization and globalization, in establishing the global prominence of English. Kachru's (1992) model of World Englishes remains fundamental in categorizing the global variations of English. His concept of concentric circles, which delineates the spread of English, has evolved, with scholars like Jenkins (2007) advancing the understanding of "English as a Lingua Franca" (ELF) and its implications as a globalized communicative resource.

In this connection, the status of English in Pakistan has garnered significant academic attention, reflecting the complex sociolinguistic landscape of the country. Kachru's influential model of 'World Englishes' (Kachru, 1985; cf. Brown & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015) has been instrumental in understanding the global spread of English, particularly in post-colonial societies like Pakistan. English gained prominence during British colonial rule and has maintained its importance since Pakistan's independence in 1947. Rahman's (1996) seminal work, *Language and Politics in Pakistan*, explores the sociolinguistic dimensions of language use in Pakistan, highlighting the role of English in education, administration, and elite discourse. His study emphasizes the sociopolitical factors shaping language policies in Pakistan. English remains a crucial element of the educational system of the country.

Nevertheless, the Grammar-Translation Method (GTM) has long been a dominant approach to teaching foreign languages in Pakistan, with many students relying on translation to understand English. The influence of GTM dates back to the colonial era when English was introduced through traditional pedagogical methods (Rahman, 2002). The historical roots of the method and the impact of colonial language policies on language teaching provide context for its continued prevalence in the country.

Research on the use of GTM in Pakistani classrooms highlights both its implementation and effectiveness. Ahmed (2019) examined GTM in English classrooms, identifying challenges faced by teachers and the impact of the method on student learning outcomes. Gouadec (2007) observed a shift in the perception of translation, evolving from a pastime to a globally recognized profession. Successful interlingual translation, however, remains challenging without a deep understanding of both cultures. Nida (1964) emphasized the crucial role translators play in conveying messages, meanings, and cultural elements seamlessly from the source language to the target language, aiming for universal

acceptance. Baker (1992) recognized that mastering idiomatic and fixed expressions is a demanding skill that requires expertise. Effective translation requires more than bilingual proficiency; it demands bicultural understanding, particularly of the culture and unique expressions of the target language. This cultural influence is particularly evident in the translation of idiomatic expressions (Min, 2007).

Needless to say, any translation is prone to lexical and syntactic errors. Translation plays a crucial role in making literary and educational content accessible to diverse linguistic communities, but it presents significant challenges, particularly in translating literary works from English to Urdu. Literary translation involves complicated decisions regarding language, culture, and stylistic nuances. Venuti (1995) introduced the concepts of “foreignization” and “domestication” in translation, emphasizing the challenge of preserving the cultural and linguistic elements of the source text while adapting it to the target audience.

A point in case is the identification of lexical errors which has been a key focus in translation studies. Baker (1992) highlighted the complexities of translating lexical items, stressing the importance of cultural equivalence and context for ensuring accurate and meaningful translations. Syntactic errors can also disrupt the coherence and meaning of a text. Nida (1964) underlined the significance of maintaining syntactic structures across languages and pointed out potential pitfalls in transferring sentence structures from English to the target language.

In an educational setting, Sultan (2015) explored the syntactic and lexical errors made by Pakistani students in English-to-Urdu translation assignments, offering insights into the challenges learners face. The Urdu language, with its rich cultural and linguistic diversities, presents unique challenges in translation. Ahmed (2019) discussed issues in translating English literary texts into Urdu, highlighting specific difficulties arising from different language structures. Farman (2019) investigated syntactic errors in translation in his study on intermediate classes at government colleges in Lahore, revealing that these errors stemmed from the influence of Urdu and a lack of English proficiency.

Further research on translation errors includes Shiddiq et al. (2023), who examined lexical and grammatical errors in Indonesian-English translations by EFL learners, identifying common mistakes such as omissions and misformations. Jabak (2023) analyzed lexical and syntactic errors in the translation of English news headlines into Arabic by Omani students, finding issues with abbreviations, proper nouns, and journalistic vocabulary. Similarly, Obeidat (2022) focused on syntactic errors in translating COVID-19 documents from English to Arabic, revealing challenges in maintaining syntactic structures. Then there are Putri and Sujarwati (2021), who analyzed syntactic errors in abstracts written by communication students, finding tense-related issues to be the most common problem. They emphasized the importance of teaching English tenses in academic writing for non-English speakers (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2007b, 2018) and

recommended future studies explore other error sources, such as morphological and lexical errors.

These researches highlight the diverse challenges in translation, particularly in language pairs like English-to-Urdu, where syntactic and lexical errors are prevalent due to cultural and structural differences. Studies by Sultan (2015), Ahmed (2019) and Farman (2019) revealed that these errors often result from Urdu's influence and insufficient English proficiency. Further research, including work by Putri and Sujarwati (2021), Obeidat (2022), Jabak (2023), and Shiddiq et al. (2023), emphasize the need for improved translation training and highlight the recurring issues with lexical and syntactic accuracy across various languages and contexts.

In this connection, Baker's (1992) translation strategies, as outlined in her work, *In Other Words: A Course Book on Translation*, provide a reliable theoretical framework for understanding the translation process. Baker (1992) defined non-equivalence at the word level as situations where the target language lacks a direct counterpart for a word in the source text. The complexity of addressing this challenge can vary significantly depending on the nature of the non-equivalence. Managing different types of non-equivalence requires employing a range of strategies, from straightforward solutions to more complex and demanding approaches. The context and purpose of translation further influence the choice of strategies, eliminating some options while favoring others.

Examples of common non-equivalence scenarios at the word level across various languages include (1) culture-specific concepts, (2) the source language concept being not lexicalized in the target language, (3) the source language word being semantically complex, (4) source and target languages meaning difference, (5) the target language lacking a superordinate, (6) the target language lacking a specific term (hyponym), (7) differences in physical and interpersonal perspectives, (8) differences in expressive meaning, (9) differences in form, (10) differences in the frequency and purpose of specific forms, and (11) use of loan words in the source text.

Baker (1992) asserted that in instances of non-equivalence, the source language term may encompass a concept that is entirely unfamiliar within the target culture—is culture-specific. This concept, whether abstract or concrete, for example, could relate to religious beliefs, social customs, or specific types of cuisine. Such concepts, commonly referred to as 'culture-specific', present a unique challenge in translation, as they involve conveying not only linguistic meaning but also cultural nuances that may be alien to the target audience.

Similarly, the source language concept may not be lexicalized in the target language. As asserted by Baker (1992), in certain cases, a concept present in the source language may exist within the target culture but lacks a designated word, so meaning it is not lexicalized. For example, the term 'savory' does not have a direct equivalent in many languages, although the concept it represents is readily

understandable. The challenge lies not in the unfamiliarity with the idea but in the absence of a specific word in the target language to articulate it.

Sometimes the source language word is semantically complex. Baker (1992) stated that semantic complexity in source language words poses a significant challenge in translation. Unlike morphological complexity, which pertains to the complex structure of a word, semantic complexity can be found even in monomorphemic words. Essentially, a single morpheme can, at times, convey a greater array of meanings than an entire sentence. Languages naturally evolve concise expressions to discuss significant and frequently mentioned complex concepts.

Likewise, source and target languages may distinguish meaning. Differences in the number of distinctions made between source and target languages are common in translation. What might be considered a crucial matter in one language may not be perceived as relevant in another. The interpretation of meaning can vary, highlighting the importance of navigating these distinctions during the translation process.

Still another complexity arises when the target language lacks a superordinate. In the target language, there may be specific words (i.e., hyponyms) but a lack of a general term (i.e., a superordinate) to encompass the entire semantic field. Cultural and psycholinguistic differences often result in translation equivalents that convey only partial meanings (Leemets, 1992). For instance, Russian lacks a direct equivalent for the term 'facilities', which refers to equipment, buildings, services, etc. (Kotz, 1965), provided for a specific activity or purpose. Thus this becomes challenging in technical and marketing terminology, where Russian lacks equivalents for many Western concepts (Holden et al., 2008), leading to potential misunderstandings (Qani, 2023).

Sometimes, the target language lacks a specific term (hyponym). Baker (1992) posited that while languages often have general terms (i.e., superordinates), they may lack specific terms (i.e., hyponyms). This occurs because languages prioritize distinctions that are relevant to their specific cultural or environmental context.

Still another source of mismatch between source and target languages is the differences in physical and interpersonal perspectives. That is, the significance of physical perspective varies between languages. Physical perspective refers to the spatial relationship between objects or people and a specific location. For instance, Japanese distinguishes the act of giving with six different verbs—*yaru*, *ageru*, *moral*, *kureru*, *itadaku*, and *kudasaru*—depending on the relationship between the giver and recipient.

Differences in expressive meaning is another source of translation difficulty. Baker (1992) explained that while a word in the target language may have the same propositional meaning as its source language counterpart, it can carry a different expressive meaning. These differences, whether subtle or significant, can complicate translation. Adding expressive meaning in translation is often easier than removing it. When the target language equivalent is more neutral than the

source language term, translators can introduce evaluative elements using modifiers, adverbs, or other strategic terms.

The source and the target language may also have differences in form when a form present in the source language may lack a direct counterpart in the target language. This is particularly true for certain English suffixes and prefixes that convey specific meanings. For example, English forms word pairs such as employer/employee, trainer/trainee, and payers/payees; suffixes such as -ish (e.g., boyish, hellish, greenish) and -able (e.g., conceivable, retrievable, drinkable) may also not have equivalents in other languages.

Differences in frequency and purpose of specific forms may also exist. Even when a form has a direct equivalent in the target language, differences in frequency of use or intended purpose may still arise. For example, English often uses the continuous -ing form in binding clauses, a construction that may not be as prevalent in other languages.

Finally, the use of loan words in the source text may cause issues. Baker (1992) highlighted the challenges posed by loan words in the source text. In addition to their propositional meaning, loan words such as *au fait*, *chic*, and *alfresco* often carry a prestige value, enhancing the sophistication of the text. This touch nuance is often lost in translation, as finding an equivalent loan word with the same connotation in the target language can be difficult. For example, the word *dilettante* is a loan word in English, Russian, and Japanese, but it lacks an equivalent in Arabic.

3. Method

3.1. Materials

The book selected for investigating translation errors is *Dogar's Intermediate English Literature, Part 1*. The researchers examined three out of the 22 chapters in the book. The chapters used as the corpus for this study are:

- Chapter 5, titled "Why Not Stay Home?" by Aldous Huxley,
- Chapter 6, titled "Amateur Athletics" by Chris Chataway, and
- Chapter 8, titled "Are Women Human?" by Dorothy Sayers.

Although the book contains over twenty essays, only these three were selected for this study due to the extensive nature of the errors identified, making it impractical to analyze all chapters. This selective approach allowed for a more detailed and thorough investigation of the prevalent translation issues. Chapter 5 spans pages 136 to 143, Chapter 6 spans pages 148 to 153, and Chapter 8 begins on page 165 and concludes on page 168. The book is published by Dogar Publishers, a leading national and international publisher, that has pioneered book publishing since 1948.

3.2. Procedure

The data collection involved a meticulous comparative analysis between the English source texts and their corresponding Urdu translations in the selected chapters. The researchers conducted a line-by-line examination to identify discrepancies and instances of translation errors. Each occurrence of a lexical or syntactic error was carefully documented and categorized.

The collected data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis, guided by Baker's (1992) theoretical framework on non-equivalence at the word level in translation. Each identified translation error was classified according to Baker's 11 categories of non-equivalence—see section 2 (above).

4. Results

Approximately 18 syntactic errors were identified in the translation of three chapters. The data showed that this error type can be further categorized into four themes: (a) repetition and redundancy, (b) incorrect literal translation, (c) misunderstood sentence structure, and (d) omission. Note that some data may show overlapping in the errors, but this means that a datum may contain more than one errors.

As for repetition and redundancy, five cases were categorized in this error type: (a) redundant use of words, (b) excessive repetition of words, (c) repetition of some sentence structures in a phrase, (d) overelaboration in translating, and (e) use of unnecessarily lengthy and repetitive phrases. Redundant use of words diminishes the variety and richness of expression. Redundancy could have been avoided by employing synonyms or alternative phrasing for smoother and more diverse linguistic flow. Minimizing redundancy can create a more concise and effective translation. By overusing certain words, the translation loses some of its clarity and impact, making it feel monotonous. There were cases in the corpus where a word-for-word translation mirrored the structure of the English text too closely. This translation lacks the natural fluency expected in Urdu and could have benefited from rephrasing to capture the original sentence's meaning while maintaining linguistic elegance. A more idiomatic approach would have preserved the intent without sounding mechanical and/or repetitive. Overelaborated translation—e.g., of “sympathizing” which may not have a direct equivalent in Urdu—was another problem where the added phrases created unnecessary complexity. A simpler translation would have conveyed the meaning more effectively without overcomplicating the text. There were also instances of repetition and redundancy where the source text expressed ‘frustration with the typewriter’, but the translation added excessive detail, repeating the idea of discarding the typewriter and introducing the unnecessary action of “breaking” it. This over-expansion of imagery detracts from the original sentence's concise ‘frustration’, and this leads to a diluted and less focused translation.

As for incorrect literal translation, there were cases where the translation fails to capture the subtleties of the original text. The translation of "The places which it is socially smart to have," for instance, had distorted the meaning by implying "smart places" rather than the intended concept of being socially adept. Here, the translation loses the essence of a "socially smart person," thereby misrepresenting the original idea. Similarly, the literal translation of "The jazz band played on monotonously" resulted in an awkward Urdu translation which mirrors the English structure too closely, leading to unnatural repetition. A more idiomatic translation would better preserve the sentence's flow in Urdu. "The boatmen drew up" was inaccurately translated suggesting they were standing rather than bringing the boat to a halt. A more precise translation should reflect that the boatmen stopped the boat. Similarly, the Urdu translation of the phrase "stood the church" had altered the meaning entirely. Instead of describing the church's static location, the translation shifts the focus to movement toward the church, losing the original spatial imagery. Likewise, the sentence "We read and travel, not that we may broaden and enrich our minds, but that we may pleasantly forget they exist" was also mistranslated, with the "not that" and "but that" constructions incorrectly interpreted whereby distorting the contrast between the two clauses. There are other errors where the Urdu translation suffers from partial translation and improper placement of phrases, awkwardly splitting and misplacing the final clause in Urdu. Similarly, the distortion of "At the point of greatest enthusiasm in my own athletic career" in the word-for-word Urdu translation alters the original meaning by focusing on emotions instead of the timing and context of the athlete's enthusiasm. Unnecessary additions and omitting essential words from the original text like "other" and "therefore" were also observed. Changes in meaning also resulted in mistranslations. For instance, the helping verb "does not" was mistakenly translated, changing the meaning from "does not" to "cannot," which misinterprets the intent of the original sentence. Overcomplication of the translation of "washing and cooking," added excessive cultural detail that was unnecessary whereas simplifying the phrase would better convey the original meaning. Finally, the incorrect literal translation of the phrase "damning and blasting the typewriter" as throwing and breaking it, turned the figurative expression into a literal action. This mistranslation alters the emotional tone of the sentence, shifting from an expression of frustration to a physical act, thereby losing the intended emotional nuance of the original text.

Misunderstood sentence structure was also observed in the corpus. The phrase "Still more courageously determined are their female companions," for instance, was mistranslated, and the word "still" was incorrectly translated, losing the intended meaning of "despite the fact." This mistranslation alters the subtlety and context of the original sentence. The phrase "staggering groups" was entirely omitted from the translation, and the word "departed" was inaccurately translated, further lessening the meaning of the sentence. There was also a case where only the first clause in a multi-clause source text was translated, with the rest of the sentence left untranslated, leading to a significant loss of meaning.

Omissions were also observed. The phrase “in staggering groups” was completely omitted from the translation. This omission removes the critical detail of ‘guests leaving in groups’, which only conveys the idea of couples departing. The “staggering” aspect, which suggests an image of disorganized or unstable movement was also left out, thus significantly altering the original imagery of the sentence and distorting its meaning. The phrase “stood the church” was also omitted, with the translation focusing on action—they went to the church—instead of the static image of the church standing at a distance, so shifting the emphasis from spatial description to action. The phrase “Work is notoriously a curse” was entirely left untranslated, with only the latter part of the sentence rendered, leaving out a key element of the meaning of the sentence.

In addition to syntactic errors, there were also lexical errors in the Urdu translation of the corpus at hand. A total of 45 lexical errors were identified in the translation of the three chapters. The observed ‘lexical’ errors can further be categorized into seven themes: (a) misinterpretation or misrepresentation of meaning, (b) over-simplification, (c) omission of key words, (d) excessive literal translation, (e) cultural misalignment, (f) redundancy, and (g) misuse of synonyms.

Seven cases of misinterpretation or misrepresentation of meaning were found. The transliteration of the word “Tourist” without conveying the meaning and cultural nuance of the original term was a lexical error. “Defiant” was translated in such a way that shifted the focus from a mental or emotional defiance to a physical action, and this alters the intended meaning. Similarly, “Motives” was translated in a broad sense that does not capture the specific intent behind “motives.” Likewise, “thronged” was mistranslated failing to express the sense of the ‘crowding or bustling movement’ implied in the source text. The translation of “specious” lost the crucial nuance of ‘something being deceptively attractive’, while “Relapse” was misinterpreted as a ‘literal physical action’, rather than the concept of ‘falling back into a previous state’. Finally, the mistranslation of the term “snobbery” offered a vague explanation that does not capture the negative connotations of the original word.

As for over-simplification, seven errors were found in the corpus. In the translation of “Disillusionment,” the term reduces the deeper sense of disillusionment to mere hopelessness, missing the emotional complexity of the original word. Similarly, “Genuine” is translated into a too general Urdu word to capture the specific sense of authenticity implied by the source word. The translation of “Exciting” conveys a sense of grandeur or magnificence rather than the intended feeling of excitement in an experience. Likewise, “Curiosity” is rendered into a vague phrase that fails to fully express the inquisitive nature of the original term. The Urdu translation of the word “Supposed” has oversimplified the nuances of presupposition and assumption of the source language. Likewise, the Urdu translation of “Bright air of discovery” over-simplifies the metaphorical sense of discovery, losing the original’s subtlety. Lastly, the translation of “Still” simplifies its contextual meaning, failing to convey its full implications.

Omission of key words in Urdu translations were also a type of lexical error. Seven cases were observed all of which significantly impact the conveyed meaning and imagery. The word “rotting” is omitted entirely, which diminishes the imagery and detail of the source sentence. Similarly, the omission of “immediately” removes the sense of urgency from the source text. The translation of “Humdrum” fails to capture the sense of monotony, as the term is left untranslated in Urdu whereby creating a gap in the description. The absence of “In my opinion” weakens the subjective tone and personal perspective of the original text. The word “Really” is also omitted, affecting the intended emphasis and intensity. Moreover, “nodded over” is mistranslated which misses the subtlety and nuance of the original action. Lastly, “departed” is mistranslated whereby simplifying the term to a generic verb and losing the specific connotation of leaving or departing.

The six instances of excessive literal translation observed in the Urdu corpus also were of a lexical nature.

The translation of “The jazz band played on monotonously” results in a word-for-word structure that feels repetitive and lacks the fluidity needed in the target language. Similarly, the expression “Damn and blast” was translated literally which fails to capture the idiomatic tone, distorting the intended meaning of the source text. The phrase “One and all” was mistranslated into a direct translation that does not align with the idiomatic feel of the original. The translation of “Disastrously” introduces redundancy, diluting the precise impact of the word. Additionally, “pathetic” was translated into Urdu in such a way that it misinterprets the negative connotation of the original term. Finally, “Snobbery” was overly interpreted whereby failing to capture the deep meaning of the word and resulting in an excessively literal and inadequate translation.

Four cases of cultural misalignment were also observed and classified as lexical errors. These cases of mistranslations demonstrate cultural and contextual misalignments that impact their accuracy and effectiveness. The phrase “bright air of discovery” is mistranslated and fails to fully convey the original deep meaning and cultural resonance of the metaphor. Similarly, the idiom “day in and day out” is rendered into a literal translation that does not capture the sense of monotony and repetitive routine implied by the original phrase. The term “tentative” is mistranslated and reflects general uncertainty rather than the specific sense of hesitancy or provisional nature intended. Lastly, the word “wished” is also mistranslated into a term that lacks the hopeful intent and desire implied by the source language “wished,” thus diminishing the original sentiment.

Four cases of redundancy were also categorized under lexical errors. They all exhibit issues of redundancy and misapplication. The term “snobbery,” for instance, is consistently mistranslated into a phrase that fails to capture the nuanced meaning of the original and introduces repetitive errors. Likewise, “rotting” is inaccurately used as an adjective for a ‘motorboat’, creating redundancy in the sentence structure by applying an inappropriate descriptor. Similarly, the Urdu translation of “complete change” redundantly employs both

'very' and 'changes' to convey the concept of change. Lastly, the term "poor" is mistranslated and merely repeats the concept of poverty without adding any new insight, leading to unnecessary redundancy.

Finally, five cases of the misuse of synonyms were also observed and categorized as lexical errors. The translation of these terms reveals significant misinterpretations and shifts in meaning. The term "reason," for instance, is mistranslated and inaccurately emphasizes emotional aspects rather than the 'logical' sense of the original word. Similarly, the Urdu rendering of "stale" shifts the meaning from "overused" or "unoriginal" to a "loss of interest," thus altering the original nuance. The Urdu translation of "disgruntled" uses a broader term for frustration, missing the specific sense of 'dissatisfaction' implied by the original word in the source language. Likewise, "besetting" is mistranslated into the Urdu word meaning 'attractive' rather than conveying the notion of 'something that continuously troubles or harasses'. Lastly, the term "exacting" is mistranslated and introduces a harsher connotation than the original term intended, thus altering its precise meaning.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study reveal significant lexical errors in the translation of the three selected chapters, highlighting issues that impact the accuracy and coherence of the translated text. Notably, the translations frequently suffered from omissions and inaccuracies that distorted the meaning of the sentences. Literal word-for-word translations led to expressions in Urdu that often felt artificial and lacked the nature of the original English text. This observation aligns with Sultan's (2015) assertion that the Urdu language presents unique challenges in translation due to its rich cultural and linguistic variances.

These translation issues appear to stem from the influence of the translator's first language—or what Salmani Nodoushan (2018) has called 'transfer' or 'carry over'; this can lead to distortions in the meaning of the source text. In this connection, Gouadec (2007) has emphasized that 'interlingual translation' is particularly challenging without a deep understanding of both cultures involved. The current study identified specific instances where adjectives were replaced with unrelated nouns, indicating a lack of contextual adaptation. This finding is consistent with Jabak's (2023) analysis of errors in translating English news headlines into Arabic, where lexical and syntactic errors, including misinterpretations of abbreviations and proper nouns, were prevalent.

Furthermore, the translation often involved repeated conjunctions and inconsistent tense usage, with some 'helping verbs' mistranslated. These issues echo Putri and Sujarwati's (2021) study, which found that tense-related errors were among the most common in abstract translations. Their study also highlighted problems with word order, incomplete grammar, and conjunction usage, reflecting similar challenges in this study. The repetition of adverbs in the target language also suggests a need for more varied and contextually appropriate

expressions, as supported by Shiddiq et al. (2023), who found common errors in Indonesian-English translations including (a) omissions, (b) confusion of sense relations, and (c) distortions.

Verb repetition and sentence structure redundancy further underscore the impact of the word-for-word approach on the coherence of the target text. Nida (1964) emphasized the importance of maintaining syntactic structures across languages, and thus this statement leads to translators' awareness against the direct transfer of sentence structures from English to Urdu. Untranslated words in the text highlight the necessity of capturing the full meaning of the source text. The use of generic terms when specific Urdu equivalents are available reflects a need for greater linguistic precision, consistent with Farman's (2019) findings, where errors were linked to a deficient understanding of English and the influence of Urdu. Furthermore, the translation of idioms into literal renditions often led to significant changes in the meaning of the source text. This highlights the importance of considering cultural, cognitive, and contextual factors when translating idiomatic expressions. Min (2007) also emphasized the impact of cultural influences on translation, particularly when dealing with idiomatic expressions.

At the lexical level, the study identified several issues, including untranslated words, incorrect translations, and literal renditions that overlooked contextual considerations. The pairing of words with redundant expressions, even when concise equivalents existed, further complicates the translation. Misclassifying adverbs as adjectives due to literal translation was another notable issue. Additionally, translating idioms into individual words significantly altered the intended meaning of the text. Hence, the inclusion of borrowed words, despite the availability of suitable Urdu equivalents, likely affected the coherence and authenticity of the translation. Overall, the observed translation approach leans towards a word-for-word method, as categorized by Baker (1992), which prioritizes proximity to the source text while often disregarding contextual and cultural matters.

6. Conclusion

This study identifies lexical and syntactic errors in English literature translated into Urdu in *Dogar's Intermediate English Literature, Part 1*. The analysis of the translation errors reveals significant challenges in achieving accuracy and cultural alignment. The prevalent issues in syntactic errors and lexical errors ranged from repetition and redundancy, incorrect literal translation, misunderstood sentence structure, and omission (i.e., syntactic errors), and misinterpretation or misrepresentation of meaning, over-simplification, omission of keywords, excessive literal translation, cultural misalignment, redundancy, and misuse of synonyms (i.e., lexical errors).

These errors demonstrate a need for improved contextual adaptation and linguistic precision. The study highlights how these errors distort meaning and

impact the coherence of the translated text. By identifying specific patterns of error, including misuse of synonyms and redundant expressions, the findings point out the importance of a suitable approach that balances the reliability to the source text with sensitivity to cultural and contextual factors. Thus, translators need to integrate a deeper understanding of both languages and cultures to enhance the quality and authenticity of translations.

This study is limited by its focus on a specific set of translation errors within a confined range of text and may not capture the full spectrum of issues encountered in broader translation contexts. Additionally, the analysis does not account for the translator's background or the specific translation strategies employed, which could influence error patterns. Future research should expand the dataset to include a wider variety of texts and translation contexts, and consider incorporating translator profiles to better understand the impact of individual differences on translation quality.

Authors' Statement

All authors affirm that they collaborated on the discussion and creation of this work. The first author came up with the concept and gathered the information, and the second and third authors worked on the manuscript, editing and refining it.

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